

ProteoForce

D1.1 Project quality plan

Name of project: Establishing Slovakia's First Cutting-Edge Advanced Laser Tweezers Laboratory for In-Depth Analysis of Molecular Forces in Clinically Relevant Hsp70 clients

Code: 09I03-03-V03-00008

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No. 09I03-03-V03-00008

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APPROVALS

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Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the authors.

ABBREVIATIONS

D1.1	Deliverable 1.1 a pod.
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DoW	The Description of Work
EC	European Commission
FR	Final Report
GA	Grant Agreement
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IR	Interim Report
Mi	Milestone
NP	Non-Public
NV1	Nezávislý Výskum 1 – označenie pracovného balíka, a pod.
P	Public
PDF	Portable Data File
PI	Principal Investigator
PM/FM	Project Manager/Financial Manager
PMT	Project Management Board
PQP	Project Quality Plan
SO	Specific Objectives
t.b.d	to be determined
UPJS	Univerzita Pavla Jozefa Šafárika v Košiciach
WP	Work Package
WP	Work Package Leader

SUMMARY

Task 1.1. Quality assurance and risk management

Duration: Month 01.-07.

This Operational management guideline represents basic rules for the Project management team (PMT) and will be gradually completed by another important issue (depending on the project implementation and development). The overall management structure was custom-tailored to reflect the real needs of the Project, with stringent control mechanisms while avoiding excessive administrative complexity and effort & resource wasting.

In this report, we outline the management structure, roles, responsibilities, conflict resolution, intellectual property issue, risk analysis, and decision-making procedures. PMT consists of (top-down) principal investigator (PI) as primarily responsible for the project coordination, Project Manager/Financial Manager (PM/FM) and Work Package Leaders (WPL1-4) as executive management. All activities are coordinated under leadership of the PI and managed i.e. effectively executed by PM and WPL1-4.

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1. PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

The present document is an internal guidance document from the start of the project to the final acceptance of the final report. Any changes must be approved by the Project Management Team (PMT) and included in a revised version of the present document.

This document defines a quality strategy providing a cohesive focus on the critical phases of the project in a structured and integrated way, the definition of explicit evaluation criteria by which the work will be measured as it progresses, and the quality assurance process.

2. PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Project management will ensure that the project will be implemented according to the goals and objective of the project ProteoForce:

- an appropriate management framework securing efficient communication and collaboration (including evaluation of the project activities) between the participants is put in place,
- monitoring the implementation of necessary changes within the work plan,
- all the project activities are appropriately coordinated and aimed at the achievement of the Project objectives and maximizing the project impact,
- the Project is completed within the planned timescale, and resources and on an appropriate quality level.

2.1. Management structure and decision-making

Organizational structure is kept lean and simple to respect the budget and timeline. Project starts on January 2024 and ends in June 2026 with overall duration of 30 month – in accordance with the project description.

2.2. Project Management Team (PMT)

The Project Management Team shall monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Project as coordinated by the Principal Investigator.

The main responsibilities of the PMT:

- ✓ Assist with project implementation
- ✓ Monitoring progress
- ✓ Ensuring achievement of the main project objectives
- ✓ Deciding about issues related to dissemination

- ✓ Deciding about budget and resource allocation
- ✓ Management of Intellectual Property
- ✓ Ensuring the quality of the outputs of the project, and of the deliverables in particular A list of issues where the PMT will have specific decision power:
- ✓ Work plan modifications
- ✓ Action plans
- ✓ Monitoring progress in the different work packages and in the project as a whole
- ✓ Risk assessment and activation of contingency plans where needed
- ✓ Progress assessment based on deliverables and milestones
- ✓ Re-distribution of resources between WPs to achieve a more efficient work flow

PI will authorize the PM and WPL to take appropriate actions to implement the decisions taken.

2.2.1. Project Coordinator

The project will be coordinated by the **Principal Investigator (PI)**, who possesses extensive expertise in biophysics, nanotechnology, and single-molecule force spectroscopy. Project coordinator and Principal Investigator will be used as synonyms within the project description. The PI will oversee the entire project, ensuring the coordination and efficient execution of activities.

The project will adopt a proactive management approach, emphasizing effective communication, team collaboration, and adherence to timelines. The PI will provide leadership, support, and mentorship to team members, fostering a productive and innovative research environment. Project resources, including laboratory equipment and funding, will be allocated appropriately to ensure the smooth implementation of experimental procedures. ProteoForce project management is committed to ensuring gender equality and equal opportunities within the project. Strategies will be implemented to promote diversity and inclusivity. The project team will actively seek to recruit researchers from diverse backgrounds and encourage the participation of underrepresented groups. Efforts will be made to balance gender representation in the team to ensure equal opportunities for all researchers involved. Additionally, the project will support work-life balance and provide equal access to career development opportunities for all team members.

2.2.2. Project Manager/Financial Manager (PM/FM)

Project manager assists the PI and is responsible for:

- ✓ ensuring a smooth flow of work and decision procedures and communication with VAIA (Research and Innovation Authority) and VA (Research Agency)
- ✓ planning, co-ordination the management of technical and administrative work
- ✓ risks monitoring
- ✓ ensuring co-operation among partners, anticipating and managing potential conflicts
- ✓ keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available
- ✓ transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned
- ✓ organization of workshops, outgoing and incoming visits and trainings (in collaboration with WPs leaders)
- ✓ collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the Funding Authority
- ✓ managing the dissemination and outreach program.

2.2.3. Relation to UPJS Administration Office

Administration tasks related to the project are managed by PM/FM assigned from CCVaPP Office of UPJS. The composition of the PMT (Table 1):

Table 1. Project Management Team composition

Name	Position in the Project
Gabriel Žoldák	Principal Inverstigator
Katarína Pezlárová	Project manager/Financial manager
Ondrej Ragač	WP1 Leader
Daniel Jancura	WP2 Leader
t.b.d	WP3 Leader
Pavol Miškovský	WP4 Leader

2.2.4. Work Packages Leaders (WPLs)

The project team will consist of skilled researchers, postdoctoral fellows, and research interns, each assigned specific responsibilities. WP Leader are the coordinators of the WP based on their expertise and training. The project will be structured into well-defined work packages (WP) and tasks, as outlined in the proposal. Each work package will have clear objectives, deliverables, and milestones, ensuring a systematic approach to achieving the project's overall goals. Regular meetings will be held to discuss progress, address challenges, and make necessary adjustments to the project plan. Communication channels will be established to facilitate collaboration with potential research partners and stakeholders in Slovakia and Europe (SO7). Work packages Leaders as WP coordinators assigned thereto (Table 2):

Table 2. Assigned WP coordinators

Work package	Work packages Leaders
Work package 1: Experimental research on bio-constructs for optical tweezers, lab Installation, Management	Ondrej Ragač
Work package 2: Single-molecule Mechanics of Hsp70 clients	Daniel Jancura
Work package 3: Research on selected Protein Targets based on national collaborative network and Training for early-stage researchers.	t.b.d.
Work package 4: Research on selected Protein Targets based on international collaborative network, dissemination and communication	Pavol Miškovský

3. INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

3.1. Communication platform, exchange tool

Regular meetings will be held to discuss progress, address challenges, and make necessary adjustments to the project plan. Communication channels will be established to facilitate collaboration with potential research partners and stakeholders in Slovakia and Europe (SO7)

Internal communication will run on **MS Teams or Google Meet platform** (Table 3). It will be used for online meetings, document sharing and storage (including the latest list of e-mail contacts of the project members). One of the folders will contain all used project document templates. Sensitive documents will be placed in the internal project storage.

Table 3. MS Teams platform

Platform/Tool	What purpose	Type of communication
MS Teams	documents, templates list of contacts, calendar, reminder	internal
MS Teams, Google Meet	videoconferences	internal, external, partners and collaborators
E-mail	Information among members, communication with potential commerce partners, questionnaires	internal, external

3.2. Meetings

With the view of the size and composition of the ProteoForce project/collaborations, the following types of meetings are planned during the project implementation:

Kick-off meeting took place when all relevant project coordinating documents are finalized (09-10/2024).

Project Management Team meetings take place at least once a year – see Table 4.

Regular progress meetings are *ad hoc* basis to monitor and verify the work progress of relevant WPs. These meetings will help update project status on a regular basis as well as having the opportunity to discuss technical, operational, financial and administrative issues. Meetings are convened by Project Manager in cooperation with the Project PI. Meeting participants are members of PMT. When necessary, the progress meetings will be organized on an *ad hoc* basis. Ad hoc meetings will be convened at the initiative of any member of PMT. Meetings will be organized if needed by PI. These meetings will be held on regular or irregular basis, depending on the type of activities and their duration.

3.2.1. Minutes of meetings

Minutes of all meeting listed in the Table 4 are mandatory. Minutes of meeting template is available. Minutes will be prepared by WPL1 within 2 weeks following the meeting. In the absence of WPL1 other person will be assigned by PI. Table 4. Schedule of planned meetings during the project

Type of meeting	Project month/Intended form
Kick- off	09-10/2024
PMT meeting 1	10/2024
PMT meeting 2	10/2025
PMT meeting 3	05/2026

4. PROJECT REPORTING

4.1. Internal reporting (verbal, non-public, confidential)

Internal reporting describes the project progress monthly. Each work package coordinator, in cooperation with project partners, will communicate to the Project Coordinator a WP progress report, including the: summary of progress towards objectives, results, status of deliverables and KPIs, actual or potential problems, activities planned during the next seven months and financial summary report.

Following all WP internal progress verbal reports, a cumulative internal report notes will be created by Principal Investigator and will be used for Interim and/or Final Report (D1.2 and D1.4). Internal cumulative reports will serve as basis for elaborating the periodic and final reports. Internal reporting will include a report on dissemination, communication and exploitation activities.

The ProteoForce project is divided into following reporting periods:

- **D1.2 Interim Report** (Month 15) to provide a summary of progress made and any deviations or adjustments to the initial plan.
- **D1.4 Final Report (Month 30)** to present comprehensive procurement documents and highlight the overall achievements of the project. The Final Report will contribute to MILESTONE Mi1, signifying the establishment of Slovakia's First Cutting-Edge Advanced Laser Tweezers Laboratory.

During the ProteoForce project, we have to prepare Interim Report and Final Report. The reports will be elaborated by PI in collaboration with the Project Manager and WP leaders. Internal cumulative reports will serve as a basis for elaborating the periodic and final reports.

5. DELIVERABLES AND MILESTONES

The project will start **01/2024 and finish on 06/2026**, with an overall duration of 30 months. If there will be a delay in the start of the project (e.g. due to delayed project evaluation), we will adapt the time schedule accordingly and prioritize critical tasks.

5.1. List and Schedule

The main objectives of the ProteoForce project are achievable through the accomplishment of the deliverables in the individual WPs. Deliverables enable to monitor the project performance and are part of the project continuous reporting. Status of deliverables and milestones will be continuously monitored by PMT.

Table 5. List of deliverables

Deliverable number	Deliverable	WP	Type	Access and dissemination	Method of verification	Delivery
D1.1	DMP and PQP	NV1	Report	P	Published open access (Zenodo)	6
D1.2	Interim Report	NV1	Report	P	Published open access (Zenodo)	15
D1.3	Lab installation	NV1	Report	NP	Procurement documents and in D1.4 Final Report	17
D1.4	Final report (FR)	NV1	Report	P	Published open access (Zenodo)	30
D2.1	Proteins for tweezers	NV2	Report	P	Published open access (Zenodo)	15
D2.2	Chaperone microfluidics	NV2	Publications	P	Published open access (Zenodo)	30
D2.3	Grant submissions	NV2	Report	NP	Documents and D1.4 Final Report	30
D3.1	Interim Networking	NV3	Report	P	Details in D1.2 Interim Report, Publications	15
D3.2	Training activity	NV3	Report	P	Details in D1.4 Final Report	25
D3.3	Networking activity	NV3	Report	P	Details in D1.4 Final Report	30
D4.1	Communication Plan and joint int. research	NV4	Report	P	Details in D1.2 Interim Report, Publications	7
D4.2	10x Conferences Attendance	NV4	Report	P	Details in D1.4 Final Report	30
D4.3	Summary of Commun. and Dissemination	NV4	Report	P	Details in D1.4 Final Report	30

5.2. Quality assurance of deliverables

The quality of deliverables will be ensured by their early preparation and by reviewing process. Deliverables will be elaborated by the Task Supervisor in cooperation with the WP Leader. Thereafter, deliverables will be submitted for approval to the project partners, represented by experts in the relevant scientific field. After incorporating their comments, Deliverable will be processed by the PI and, if needed submitted to the Zenodo portal. Reviewing levels and timeline are listed in Table 6.

Table 6. Reviewing levels and timeline

Time	What (Activity)	Who
2 months before due date	Reminder to WP Leader	PMT
4 weeks before due date	Submission of the draft version of Deliverable to partners (experts)	WP Leader
2 weeks before due date	Submission of the Deliverable (approved version) to PI	PI
Due date	Submission of the Deliverable	PI

A template for all project deliverables has been elaborated and is available on the MS Teams platform in the “Templates” folder.

6. RISK MANAGEMENT

Risk Management Approach: Our approach to risk management involves acknowledging potential challenges and uncertainties and implementing measures to mitigate their impact. High-risk research questions (SO3) will be balanced with low-risk questions to diversify research outcomes and reduce the risk of uncertainties. To address the risk of grant proposal competitiveness (SO6), alternative funding sources and collaborations with national and European research institutions (SO7) will be pursued. Regular risk assessments will be conducted throughout the project, and contingency plans will be developed to address unforeseen challenges promptly. The PI will closely monitor the progress of the project and engage in open communication with the team to address any emerging risks. Regular feedback from collaborators and stakeholders will contribute to risk management and improve decision-making.

7. CONFLICT MANAGEMENT

Identification of any conflicts which arise in the project is the responsibility of all project participants. Any signs of disagreement between team members & partners should be notified to WPL.

WPL should separately contact all parties either in person or by *telephone*, to identify the different viewpoints (it is essential not to use email: that medium very often leads to a rapid escalation of disagreements). Based on the clarification of viewpoints, the manager should try to propose a solution. If one is achieved, it should be recorded in a short report; if not, no documents should be produced, and the problem escalated.

B - If level A fails, the PMT should take up the matter. At this level, all work should be in writing.

8. IPR AND KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

Strategy for knowledge management and protection is described in the ProteoForce project in detail. Due to the highly innovative profile of some scientific activities linked with the proposed project, serious attention will be paid to the **protection of intellectual property (IP)** created. This task is coordinated with the Technology and innovation park of our University, precisely by the Center of technology transfer. They are the rules defined by our University about IPR protection.

This complicated document defines all task concerning to legal rights and duties of individuals vs. University and it will serve as our guide (together with partners guidelines) for the IPR management.

9. FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT

The financial management is performed by the Project manager/Financial manager with the assistance of PMT and under guidance of PI.

10. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

We plan to communicate our findings to the scientific community and the general public through a variety of platforms, such as:

Publications: Our research findings will be published in high-impact, peer-reviewed journals. These will be accessible to the global scientific community, fostering knowledge exchange and collaboration.

Conferences and Symposia: Our team will present findings at relevant scientific conferences and symposia, both locally and internationally. This will provide opportunities for discussions and collaborations with other experts in the field.

Public Lectures and Outreach Activities: We plan to host public lectures and participate in science outreach activities to engage with the general public. This will help to increase public understanding and interest in our research.

Project Website and Social Media: A dedicated project website will be set up to provide regular updates on our progress, achievements, and upcoming activities. We also plan to utilize social media to reach a broader audience and engage in real-time interactions.

Press Releases and Media Engagement: We will work with media to disseminate our findings and their implications, thereby reaching a wider audience beyond the scientific community.

11. REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

Grant Agreement number: 09I03-03-V03-00008, “ProteoForce“ [Establishing Slovakia’s First Cutting-Edge Advanced Laser Tweezers Laboratory for In-Depth Analysis of Molecular Forces in Clinically Relevant Hsp70 clients.](#)